

NUMERICAL APPROACHES IN THE FATIGUE DAMAGE SIMULATION IN QUASI-BRITTLE MATERIALS

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Simulating fatigue damage processes has been a challenging task for researchers in various engineering fields. Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) has been extensively used with success in ductile materials, taking into account their plasticity. However, quasi-brittle materials exhibit characteristic phenomena which are difficult to simulate using CDM. An alternative approach is to use Discrete Element Methods (DEM), which involves building a spatial discretisation using nodes with masses and mechanical interaction functions represented by elements such as bars or beams. The mechanical behaviour of the solid up to the point of collapse can be represented using simple constitutive laws associated with these bonds. This work explores the possibilities of representing the evolution of damage using models based on DEM in the context of fatigue. Two examples are presented to demonstrate the capabilities of these approaches in representing the main features of fatigue methodologies.

Keywords: Fatigue, Quasi-brittle Materials, Discrete Element Method, Peridynamic.

INTRODUCTION

Quasi-brittle materials are typically heterogeneous and characterised by an anisotropic behaviour. Their damage process is governed by damage, not by plasticity. Bazant and Planas [3] proposed a methodology for representing damage in quasi-brittle materials. As pointed out by Krajinovic [4], the heterogeneity of these materials, the size effect, and the localisation process are interconnected. To convert the diffuse micro-cracking process, which could be represented with a continuum damage parameter, into a clear discontinuity, all of these factors must be taken into account.

Fatigue behaviour of heterogeneous materials is generally characterised by the S-N curve proposed by the Wöhler curve [1], where the fatigue lifetime is predicted for a given stress amplitude. According to Lorenzino and Navarro [5], among others, the S-N curve is probably the simplest and most used approach for plain specimens under fatigue. This methodology captures problems where the initiation period is more critical in the system analysed.

On the other hand, when the propagation is more important than the initiation in the fatigue process, the study of crack propagation under fatigue loading is performed with the Paris (or Paris–Ergodan) law presented in Paris & Erdogan [6]. The authors suggested that the range of the stress intensity factor, ΔK , is linked with the crack growth rate, da/dN , by a potential law characterising a stable crack propagation stage in this way. Such a stage is linked with a region of crack propagation

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initiation and a region of unstable crack growth rate.

In order to complement experimental fatigue tests, numerical methods have been used to simulate fatigue problems. The most popular is the Finite Element Method (FEM), commonly used to compute the stress state as employed by Vantadori et al. [7]. In this paper, two alternatives to FEM are employed to simulate the fatigue damage behaviour of quasi-brittle materials: (i) the Lattice Discrete Element Method (LDEM) proposed originally by Riera [9] and employed with success in the simulation of quasi-brittle materials subjected to different kind of loadings [10-12], and (ii) the Peridynamic (PD) theory proposed by Silling [13]. In both alternatives, the fracture and damage could be modelled naturally at the scale of bars in the case of the LDEM and bonds in the case of PD.

In the following, a brief description of the LDEM and PD is presented, and then two applications related to fatigue simulation of quasi-brittle materials are analysed. Finally, the conclusions are summarised.

NUMERICAL METHODS EMPLOYED

The Lattice Discrete Element method (LDEM) proposed by Riera (1984) [9]

The LDEM is based on a cubic arrangement with uniaxial elements assuming a truss-like structure; therefore, only with three degrees of freedom. The basic module is described with twenty bars and nine nodes conceived initially by Nayfeh and Hefzy [14]. The problems regarding dynamic issues assume the masses are concentrated at the nodes where the central node has half of the total mass, while each one of the remaining eight nodes has one-sixteenth of the total mass of the representative cube. The lengths of longitudinal and diagonal elements are L_n and $L_d = \sqrt{3}L_n/2$, respectively. The equations that relate the properties of the elements with the elastic constants of an isotropic medium are:

$$\delta = \frac{9\theta}{4-8\theta} \quad A_n = \frac{L_n^2(9+8\delta)}{2(9+12\delta)} \quad A_d = \frac{2\delta A_n}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (1)$$

The dynamic system enforces at every node the motion equation:

$$M\ddot{u} + C\dot{u} + f + p = 0 \quad (2)$$

where M represents the diagonalised mass matrix, u the generalised nodal displacements, C the diagonal damping matrix, $f = f(t)$ the internal forces operating on the lumped masses and $p = p(t)$ the external forces. The system is uncoupled, and a central finite differences approach can be applied to integrate the motion equation over the time domain. The nodal coordinates are updated at each time step, which allows large displacements to be accounted for naturally.

Hillerborg [15] proposed the simplest constitutive law for quasi-brittle materials, which considers a triangular Element Constitutive Relationship (ECR) at each normal and diagonal element. This law accounts for the irreversible effects of crack nucleation and propagation. Figure 1(b) illustrates the relation between force and strain, where the area below the curve defines the energy density required to fracture the cross-sectional area of the element.

Figure 1c presents a modified version of (ECR) that incorporates residual strain. All components under traction are assumed to exhibit this behavior. Additionally, due to the higher strength of quasi-fragile materials under compression loading, all elements are considered linear elastic in these circumstances. Thus, failure in compression is induced by indirect tension.

FIGURE 1: (a) LDEM discretisation strategy with the basic cubic module highlighted in red, (b) Bilinear constitutive law based on the Hillerborg, [15] (and (c) Bilinear constitutive law considering residual strains

The element axial force F depends on the axial strain ϵ . An equivalent fracture area A_i^f , where the subindex i indicates if the bar is normal (n) or diagonal (d), must satisfy the equivalence of the energy dissipated by the fracture of the continuum and its discrete representation. Therefore, the strains ϵ_p and ϵ_u (see Figure 1(b)) must be related to another material parameter, the characteristic length d_{eq} , employing the expressions:

$$\epsilon_p = \sqrt{\frac{G_f}{E d_{eq}}} \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_u = \epsilon_p d_{eq} \left(\frac{A_n^f}{A_d^f} \right) \left(\frac{2}{L_i} \right) \quad (4)$$

The unstable fracture propagation requires that the characteristic length of the structure exceeds d_{eq} . The role of the characteristic length in the fracture process is discussed by Taylor [16]. It should be noted that ϵ_u depends on the material properties and on the level of discretisation . More details about the LDEM formulation employed in this paper may be found in Birek et al., [17].

In Figure 1(c) a variation of the Constitutive law, where the residual stress is considered, is presented. This law will also be employed in the fatigue application.

The random distribution of the material properties, which consider the heterogeneity of quasi-brittle materials, is employed in the simulations by considering the fracture energy, G_f , as a random field with a probability distribution of two-parameter Weibull function, defined by the mean value and the coefficient of variation. Additionally, the G_f spatial distribution is given by the correlating lengths in the three coordinate directions. More information about random fields in the LDEM can be found in Puglia et al. [18].

Basic concepts of the Peridynamic theory

In the present Section a concise overview of the PD theory is performed. Further details can be found in Madenci et al [19]

The PD theory discretises a solid body subjected to an external loading into material particles, each of them surrounded by a neighborhood, named Peridynamic horizon, H . In Figure 2(a) shows the kinematics of a typical PD body.

The interaction force between material particle X (identified by its position vector, see Figure 2(a)) and any neighboring particle, X' , in the horizon (i.e. $X' \in H_x$, as illustrated in the same Figure

is defined by the pairwise force density function, $\mathbf{f}$. This function is a force per unit volume and represents the force vector exerted by the particle X' on the particle X [20].

The governing PD equation of motion, at a given time step, t , can be written as follows [19]:

$$\rho \dot{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{X}, t) = \int_{H_x} \mathbf{f}(\boldsymbol{\eta}, \boldsymbol{\xi}, t) dV_{x'} + \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{X}, t) \quad \|\mathbf{X}' - \mathbf{X}\| \leq \delta \quad (5)$$

where ρ is the material mass density, $\mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{X}'$ are the position vectors, $\mathbf{u}$ is the displacement vector where the upper dots over the parameter indicate temporal derivative, dV_x denotes an infinitesimal volume around the particle and $\mathbf{b}$ is the body force density.

The pairwise force density function, $\mathbf{f}$ must contain the material's constitutive information, then use the proposal presented by Silling [13] for a micro-elastic material. $\mathbf{f}$ must be derived from a scalar function $w(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta})$, then:

$$\mathbf{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta}) = \frac{\partial w(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}} \quad (6)$$

where $w(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta})$ represents the energy strain energy per volume stored in the material and could be defined as

$$w(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta}) = \frac{c(\boldsymbol{\xi})s^2(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta})|\boldsymbol{\xi}|}{2} \quad (7)$$

In the Eq. (7) the function $c(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ represents the bound micro-module, it is a parameter related to the material, that could be considered as constant. $s(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta})$ represent the bond stretch and could be expressed as:

$$s = \frac{|\boldsymbol{\xi} + \boldsymbol{\eta}| - |\boldsymbol{\xi}|}{|\boldsymbol{\xi}|} \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (7), $|\boldsymbol{\xi}|$ represents the distance between the material points linked by a bond in the undeformed configuration, and $|\boldsymbol{\xi} + \boldsymbol{\eta}|$ represents the distance between the same material points in the deformed configuration. By replacing Eq. (7) in Eq. (6), the function that defines the force exerted for the bond between the pair of material points x and x' in the formulation for an isotropic linear elastic.

$$\mathbf{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\eta}) = cs \frac{\boldsymbol{\xi} + \boldsymbol{\eta}}{|\boldsymbol{\xi} + \boldsymbol{\eta}|} \quad (9)$$

The micro-module of the bond was defined by Silling and Askari [20] for a linear material in a 2D plane strain analysis as:

$$c = \frac{6E}{\pi h \delta^3 (1-2\nu)(1+\nu)} \quad (10)$$

where E is the material Elasticity modulus, h is the thickness of the examined component and ν the Poisson's ratio.

FIGURE 2. (a) Reference configuration and deformed configuration according to PD theory, (b) Prototype Microelastic Brittle (PMB) model proposed by Silling and Askari [20]. (c) bilinear PD model presented in Cabral et al [21] and Friedrich et al [22], and (d) the bilinear PD model function of the number of loading cycles presented in Friedrich et al [23].

The critical bond stretch (see Figure 2(b)), s_0 , can be computed by:

$$s_0 = \sqrt{\frac{RG_f}{E\delta}} \quad (11)$$

being R equal to $5\pi/12$ for 2D plane strain analysis. In Silling and Askari [20], a physical meaning is proposed for horizon δ , defining this parameter as a material characteristic length that is a material property. Defined in the context of this method as the spherical radius for 3D problems when all the nodes are interconnected. This value has the same meaning as the d_{eq} presented in the LDEM method described above. Concerning this point, observe the similarity between expressions (11) and (3). In Taylor [16], a characteristic material length is also used to define failure criteria. On the other hand, [20] verified a good numerical performance maintaining $\delta=3.015\Delta$ where Δ represents the model discretisation parameter, that is, the distance between the material points. There are some strategies to overcome these restrictions in the definition of the δ . We adopt here the proposes by Cabral et al. [21] and also used in Fredrich et al. [22]. This strategy consists of defining a numerical horizon d that accomplishes the numerical condition $\delta=3.015\Delta$ and a material characteristic length δ_m . s_p the critical strain in this modified law is obtained using (11), replacing δ with δ_m . The link between δ and δ_m is performed using a bilinear law, as presented in Figure 2(c). More details about the application of this law are presented in [21] and [22]. In the context of fatigue, a preliminary proposal is presented by Friedrich et al.[23], where the damage increases with the number of loading cycles, is implemented. Figure 2(d) shows such a law inspired by that proposed in [24].

APPLICATIONS

LDEM Application: A plain plate subjected to an axial loading stress

In the present application the performance of the LDEM to model the fatigue damage is presented. The model consists of a plain plate formed by $149 \times 21 \times 3$ cubic modules with a cubic length size $L_n=7.5\text{mm}$. Typical material properties for concrete are considered: $\rho=2400 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $E=35\text{GPa}$, $G_f=160\text{N/m}$, average tensile strength, σ_t , equal to 9.8MPa , and $CV_{Gf}=70\%$. Considering $\sigma_t=E\epsilon_p$, and the Eq. (3), d_{eq} is computed as 0.058m .

Notice that:

- if G_f is a random field, we consider in the model that ϵ_p also has variability, but d_{eq} is a deterministic value.

$-\rho$, E , G_f , CV_{GF} , and d_{eq} are input parameters for the model.

In Figure 3(b), it is possible to see the characteristic of the cyclic loading applied, and in Figure 3(c), the global results in the typical S-N in log-log scale where it is possible to define two regions. The curves in blue are the results using the original bilinear law presented in Figure 1(b), and those in red are the results of the bilinear law considering residual strains presented in Figure 1(c).

Figure 4 presents the damage evolution for the model with the original bilinear law (Figure 4(a)), as well as the oscillating elastic energy and the damaged bars (blue circled) at different time steps (Figure 4(b)). The simulation effectively captures the localisation process. The undamaged bars are shown in light blue, the damaged bars in orange, and the bars that begin to damage between two successive pictures (steps 1 to 8) in dark blue.

The presented results are qualitative and only intended to demonstrate the potential of this approach. Additional applications following the same strategy are shown in Soares [25] and Giordani et al. [26].

FIGURE 3. The plain plate subjected to a uniaxial cyclic loading stress: (top) the LDEM model, (bottom left) the cyclic loading applied, and (bottom right) the result in terms of S-N curves for the original (in blue) and modified bilinear laws (in red) presented in Figures 1(b) and (c), respectively.

FIGURE 4. (top) (a) Results of the simulations using the original bilinear law (indicated with label 1 in Figure 2(c)). The Elastic Energy oscillation during the evolution with continuum line, the circles indicating when some bar reach its critical ε_p . Notice that ε_p is a random parameters function of the input. (bottom) (b) the steps 1-8 indicating in the previous plot, undamaged bar in light blue, in orange damage bars, in dark blue are indicated the new bars damaged between two successive steps.

Peridynamic application: Notched concrete beam subjected to cyclic Load

In the present application a concrete notched beam under three-point bending loading tested by Kirane and Bazant [27] is numerically simulated. The beam geometry has high, H , equal to 93mm, width, W , equal to 40mm and aspect ratio $L/H=2.4$. The notched height ratio, a/H , is equal to 0.30.

The material parameters were defined experimentally as: elastic modulus, $E=40.12\text{GPa}$, tensile failure stress, $\sigma_f=3\text{MPa}$, and fracture energy, G_f , equal to 40N/m . In the experimental campaign were carried out tested to determine the static flexural load, P_f , and after a cycled loading in the range interval of $[0.05-0.85]P_f$ was applied.

A Peridynamic simulation was performed using the model presented in Figure 5(a). Details about the bilinear law can be found in [21-22].

The input data used in the Peridynamic model are presented in Table 1. In the table also are presented some of the internal model parameters linking these values with the explanation presented in Section 2.2. The toughness was considered as a random data with $CV_{Gf}=50\%$ Weibull statistical distribution and correlation length for the random field with a $l_{cor}=0.01\text{m}$.

In Figure 5(b) the comparison between the experimental and numerical static tests are presented in terms of the load vs CMOD. In Figure 5(c) the load applied in the numerical cyclic simulation, that is $[0.05-0.85]P_f$ is presented. Figure 5(d) a comparison between experimental and numerical simulation for the fatigue tests are presented in terms of fatigue lifetime. The numerical results show a good correlation with respect to the experimental static and the fatigue tests.

TABLE 1: The Peridynamic parameters used in the application.

INPUT DATA					
Δ [mm]	E [GPa]	ρ [kg/m ³]	s_p [-]	G_f [Nm]	σ_0 [MPa]
			(Fig. 2(c))		
3.0	41.24	2400	$7.638(10)^{-5}$	72.5	3.0
INTERNAL MODEL PARAMETERS					
δ [mm]	c [N/m ⁶]	δ_m [m]	σ_0/E [-]	s_r	
3.015Δ	Eq.(10)	Eq.(11)			(Fig. 2(c))
9.045	$1.70(10)^{17}$	0.423	$7.37(10)^{-5}$		$3.33(10)^{-3}$

In TABLE 2 the comparison results between experimental and numerical are presented and the correlation was satisfactory.

Finally, in Figure 6 other results are presented: (a) the cyclic variation of the load up to the failure in one Peridynamic specimen, in grey line, whereas the black line is the static result for the same specimen; (b) the damage evolution in terms of the CMOD vs number of the cycles; (c) different fracture configurations during the simulation and the experimental final rupture configuration. The results shown above are in agreement with experimental evidences found in the literature.

FIGURE 5: A notched concrete beam subjected to a static and cyclic loading [27]: (a) the Peridynamic model, (b) the comparison between the experimental and numerical results in the static tests, (c) the load vs. time applied in the numerical fatigue simulations, and (d) the comparison between experimental and numerical result in the fatigue test (several specimens with the same statistical characteristic are simulated).

Table 2: Comparison between experimental and numerical results in terms of fatigue lifetime.

	EXPERIMENTAL	No.	NUMERICAL	ERROR
Fatigue lifetime	663±488	1	656	-1.06%
		2	909	37.10%
		3	749	12.97%
		4	452	-31.87%
		5	696	4.98%

CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, the numerical simulation of fatigue damage evolution in quasi-brittle materials was analysed by using the Lattice Discrete Element Model (LDEM) originally presented by Riera [9] and the Peridynamic theory proposed by Silling [13]. In both strategies, the modification proposed in the constitutive behaviour of the material was performed at the bar and bond levels. In the first application, for both constitutive laws (the original and modified), the results obtained show that the global behaviour in terms of the S-N relationship presents the same tendency. In the second application, a quantitative comparison is performed, and the results are in agreement with the experimental ones. Improvements in the local constitutive law used to capture different global behaviours, typically found in fatigue tests, will be the next step in this research.

FIGURE 6: Notched concrete beam subjected to a three-point bending cyclic loading: (a) the comparison between the numerical static global response and the cyclic response in terms of load vs CMOD, (b) the CMOD vs cyclic number evolution, and (c) numerical fracture configuration evolution and the final experimental fracture configuration.

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